

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Intuitive toxicology in the 21st century—Bridging the perspectives of the public and risk assessors in Europe

Angela Bearth¹ | Nicolas Roth^{2,3} | Martin F. Wilks^{2,3} | Michael Siegrist¹

¹Consumer Behavior, Institute for Environmental Decisions, ETH Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

²Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology, University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

³Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

Correspondence

Angela Bearth, Consumer Behavior, Institute for Environmental Decisions, ETH Zurich, Universitaetstrasse 22, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland. Email: angela.bearth@hest.ethz.ch

Funding information

European Union through Horizon Europe project "European Partnership for the Assessment of Risk from Chemicals (PARC)", Grant/Award Number: 101057014; Bundesamt für Gesundheit

Abstract

Three decades ago, several articles on the subjectivity in chemical risk judgments (i.e., labeled "intuitive toxicology") measured the divide between the public and toxicologists with different backgrounds regarding the validity of predicting health effects based on in vivo studies. Similar divides with impacts on societal discourse and chemical risk assessment practices might exist concerning alternative toxicity testing methods (i.e., in vitro and in silico). However, studies to date have focused either on the public's views of in vivo or stem cell testing or on experts' views of in vivo testing and potential alternatives (i.e., toxicologists and medical students), which do not allow for a direct investigation of potential divides. To fill this knowledge gap, we conducted two online surveys, involving members of the German-speaking public in Switzerland and European human health risk assessors, respectively. This article presents the results of these two surveys regarding the divide in the public's and risk assessors' perspectives on risk assessment based on in vivo, in vitro, and in silico testing. Particularly, the survey with the risk assessors highlights that, beyond scientific and regulatory barriers, alternatives to in vivo testing may encounter individual hurdles, such as higher uncertainty associated with them. Understanding and addressing these hurdles will be crucial to facilitate the integration of new approach methodologies into chemical risk assessment practices as well as a successful transition toward next-generation risk assessment, bringing us closer to a fit-for-purpose and more efficient regulatory landscape.

KEYWORDS

chemical risk assessment, intuitive toxicology, new approach methodologies, next-generation risk assessment, risk perception

1 | INTRODUCTION

1.1 | Expert disagreement about the principles of toxicology

Three decades ago, several articles on the role of subjectivity in chemical risk assessment (labeled "intuitive toxicology") were published (Kraus et al., 1992; MacGregor et al., 1999; Mertz et al., 1998; Slovic et al., 1995). The articles reported empirical studies with toxicologists and the public in the United States of America (USA), Canada, and the United Kingdom (UK) on toxicological principles and challenges (labeled "dose–response mechanism," "trust in animal and bacterial studies," "general attitudes toward chemical risk"). The core results of the articles (Kraus et al., 1992; Mertz

et al., 1998; Slovic et al., 1995) showed differences in the responses concerning toxicological principles and challenges given by toxicologists and the public from the USA, and perhaps more surprisingly, differences between toxicologists partly explained by their different backgrounds (i.e., regulation, industry, and academia), gender, and world views. The toxicologists were particularly divided regarding their trust in animal studies. For example, 55% of toxicologists agreed or strongly agreed and 41% disagreed or strongly disagreed that "the way that an animal reacts to a chemical is a reliable predictor of how a human would react to the same chemical" (4% did not know or did not have an opinion) (Kraus et al., 1992, p. 218). Similarly, 41% agreed or strongly agreed and 58% disagreed or strongly disagreed that "if a scientific study produces evidence that a chemical causes cancer in animals, then

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we can be reasonably sure that the chemical will cause cancer in humans” (1% did not know or did not have an opinion) (Kraus et al., 1992, p. 218). Similar patterns were found in replication studies in Canada and the UK (MacGregor et al., 1999; Slovic et al., 1995, 1997). Although scientific methods clearly incorporate inherent subjectivity (e.g., extrapolation assumptions and interpretation), expert disagreement about fundamental principles in toxicology had previously not been documented in a similar way. These findings are relevant because the public can be quite sensitive to expert disagreement, which might raise concerns regarding various chemical risks, reduce trust in expertise and science, and complicate the public discourse on chemical risks (Kraus et al., 1992; Renn et al., 1996; Sjöberg, 1999).

1.2 | New developments in chemical risk assessment, management, and communication

The initial article (Kraus et al., 1992) introduced the need for investigating the divide by recognizing the challenges involved in balancing the requirements of chemical risk assessment with the societal expectations of risk analysis. The authors argued “that different assumptions, conceptions, and values underlie much of the discrepancy between expert and lay views of chemical risks” (Slovic et al., 1995, p. 661). Risk assessment, management and communication, and specifically, toxicology, have evolved in the last decades to address the increasing societal, political, and ethical concerns over human health and environmental impacts from anthropogenic chemicals. The 3R principle (Russell & Burch, 1959) calls for the replacement, reduction, and refinement of *in vivo* testing through alternative methods and has been a major driver for shifting the classical animal-centric paradigm of toxicology (Grimm et al., 2023; Neuhaus et al., 2022; Pallocca et al., 2022; Tannenbaum & Taylor, 2015). New ways of testing and assessing the safety of chemical substances using new approach methodologies (NAMs) (e.g., *in vitro* and *in silico* methods) have been developed and are, albeit hesitantly, introduced to regulatory hazard and/or risk assessment practices (Ball et al., 2022; Barton-Maclaren et al., 2022; Schmeisser et al., 2023; Stucki et al., 2022; Westmoreland et al., 2022). These alternatives rely on testing microorganisms, cells, or molecules outside of a living organism (*in vitro*), simulation of physiological mechanisms or the use of computer models and large amounts of data (*in silico*). Implementing new scientific tools and approaches in the toxicity testing and assessment workflow (e.g., based on grouping/read-across, toxicokinetics, adverse outcome pathways, quantitative structure–activity relationships, omics technologies, artificial intelligence [AI], and automated processes) have and will increasingly introduce new challenges for regulatory decision-making (Myatt et al., 2018; Najjar et al., 2022; Paini et al., 2022; Punt et al., 2018; Viant et al., 2019; Wittwehr et al., 2020). These include the need for additional skills of risk assessors and managers; increased complexity in decision-making and increased (perceived) uncertainty; and the (perceived) trustworthiness of AI (Alves

et al., 2021; Wittwehr et al., 2020). The term “perceived” highlights that it is not always possible to objectively quantify uncertainty or trustworthiness (e.g., due to missing data, missing information about the underlying model or algorithm or due to unclear data quality or relevance) and that individual risk assessors or the public might use intuition, heuristics or potentially biasing signals (e.g., elicited spontaneous associations, design features of an AI tool) to judge uncertainty and trustworthiness (Bostrom et al., early view).

Recent social science research has focused on experts’ perceptions of these new developments (e.g., toxicologists, chemical risk assessors, health professionals, and medical students; Mondou et al., 2020; Pain et al., 2020; Zaunbrecher et al., 2017), the public’s perceptions of *in vivo* testing (e.g., Hagelin et al., 2003; Henry & Pulcino, 2009; Lund et al., 2014; Ormandy et al., 2013) or, less frequently, of alternatives (Critchley et al., 2013). However, we could not identify recent research that brings these two perspectives, experts and the public, together, even though there are good reasons to do so. Three of these reasons are discussed in the sections below.

1.3 | Societal debates about risk analysis

First and foremost, the “rancorous conflicts” involving regulators, environmentalists, technologists, and industrialists invoked in the original “intuitive toxicology” article (Kraus et al., 1992, p. 215) remain volatile. Specifically, numerous examples of risks exist, where experts are faced with a concerned public and technological, regulatory, or communication challenges (e.g., environmental pollution, contaminated sites, pesticide residues in food, nanomaterials in consumer products, nuclear energy, new genomic techniques, and plant breeding). Understanding what societal or ethical values, attitudes and, most importantly for this article, beliefs are prevalent among the public about the way the safety of chemicals is assessed can improve mutual understanding, help to clarify misunderstanding, or provide missing information ahead of time to avoid conflicts, low acceptance, and product or service rejections (Bearth et al., 2019; Jansen et al., 2020a; Kraus et al., 1992). Other examples exist of how social science research can contribute to improved exchanges among experts and society. For example, although in early years of investigating public perceptions of chemicals (Kraus et al., 1992; Slovic et al., 1995), the term “risk” was used in a general manner, recent research sought to understand whether the public differentiates between the concepts of risk and hazard (Freudenstein et al., 2020) or how epistemic uncertainty is best communicated (Jansen et al., 2020a; Spiegelhalter, 2017). Similarly, a series of studies based on the mental models approach highlight the value of understanding prevalent misconceptions and misunderstandings, and clarifying these in risk communication for various chemical risks, such as radon or food additives (Atman et al., 1994; Bearth et al., 2014, 2016; Saleh et al., 2019). Successful societal debates about chemical safety and risks need these insights on how to bridge science, regulatory requirements, and public perceptions.

1.4 | Concerns over chemical risks and regulatory acceptance of new methods

Second, the public is concerned with chemical risks (Dickson-Spillmann et al., 2009; Jansen et al., 2020b; Saleh et al., 2019), while simultaneously having mixed or negative feelings and attitudes toward *in vivo* testing (Lund et al., 2014; Petetta & Ciccocioppo, 2020; Williams et al., 2007). Zaunbrecher et al. (2017) conducted a survey with $N = 1381$ toxicologists (75% from North America, 15% from Europe, and 10% from other) and showed that regulatory acceptance was seen as major barrier to the use of *in vitro* or *in silico* methods. Similarly, hesitance from relevant stakeholders, specifically from regulation, over the use of alternative methods for testing and assessment has been identified as an important barrier (Schmeisser et al., 2023). Public beliefs and attitudes can have a direct (e.g., public pressure, votes and elections, and consumer decisions; Crettaz Von Roten & Bauer, 2022) and an indirect effect on regulation and regulatory acceptance of specific methods (e.g., science engagement, expectations and perceptions of risk assessors, and managers about the public reactions) (Bearth & Siegrist, 2022; Mendez et al., 2022). Failure to consider public risk perceptions and beliefs about chemical risk regulation and management can have negative impacts on the individual and societal level. Consumers' risk perceptions can increase or reduce trust in science as well as in experts and impact behavior when the public feels that risk assessment is unreliable (e.g., vaccine hesitancy, boycott of new technologies or products, backlash and protest) (Francl, 2013). Recent research has called attention to the usefulness of skepticism and critical trust for risk management compared to acceptance (Fjaeran & Aven, 2021; Walls et al., 2004); however, public distrust and rejection or cynicism regarding risk assessment hampers informed decision-making and can negatively impact society. Furthermore, reassuring consumers through information provision (e.g., on dose–response mechanisms and risk assessment) can sometimes lessen unnecessarily heightened risk perceptions, as suggested for chemicals in general (Hartings & Fahy, 2011; Saleh et al., 2020), food chemicals (Bearth et al., 2016; Dickson-Spillmann et al., 2009; Shim et al., 2011), environmental pollutants (Kay & Regional Administrator, 1989), or trace chemicals (Bearth et al., 2020, 2021).

1.5 | Analytical and heuristic strategies to judge different methods

Third, although most of the lay public is likely unaware of the new developments in risk assessment (or of methods in risk assessment in general), it is to be expected that respondents will use intuitive strategies, so-called heuristics, to evaluate the methods when confronted with them in the public discourse, when discussing them with other people or responding to questions about them (Kahneman et al., 1982; Siegrist & Bearth, 2019). Although risk assessors have more

knowledge than the public, it is also possible that risk assessors (partly) use intuitive strategies to evaluate and respond to methods that they are unfamiliar with (Schmeisser et al., 2023). A possible heuristic conceptualization of the validity of a particular test for both the public and risk assessors could be linked to the real or perceived complexity of the model. In terms of real complexity, simple models may more easily gain acceptance among end-users, such as regulatory decision-makers, due to lower entry hurdles than more complex models. Particularly, computer-based models, supported with AI and machine learning might be seen as too complex and uncertain; in short, they might be seen as a black box and, thus, might not be trusted (Alves et al., 2021; Wittwehr et al., 2020). Aside from real and perceived complexity, a variety of cues might be used to judge a model, such as the perceived similarity of the model to human biology (e.g., *in vivo* vs. *in vitro*) or the complexity of the endpoint (e.g., skin sensitization vs. cancer). These heuristic conceptualizations might directly and indirectly impact which methods will play a role in future risk assessment, particularly in the context of NAMs.

To summarize, chemical safety—and the viability of different methods to determine it—will remain in the public eye in the future and this societal pressure impacts political debates and policy decisions (Schiffelers et al., 2012). Experts are debating what risk assessment should look like in the future, specifically, which principles should underlie next-generation risk assessment (NGRA) (for a discussion see Marx-Stoelting et al. (2023) and Schmeisser et al. (2023)). To balance scientific evidence, uncertainty and subjectivity underlying regulatory risk assessment, it is useful to consider social science evidence on different perspectives. This will inform regulatory risk assessment, management and communication, support decision-making regarding various trade-offs, and counter disinformation campaigns, as, for example, highlighted by the European Food Safety Authority (2022) and various scholars in risk research (e.g., Bearth & Siegrist, 2022; Hartings & Fahy, 2011; Jansen et al., 2020a; Kasperson et al., 2022; Siegrist & Árvai, 2020).

2 | STUDY AIM

In line with the original “intuitive toxicology” articles (Kraus et al., 1992; Slovic et al., 1995), this article aimed at providing updated insights into expert and lay perspectives on chemical risk assessment for human health, specifically regarding the assumptions resulting from *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and *in silico* models and their transferability. Furthermore, it aimed at exploring how risk assessors viewed the future of risk assessment and how this is linked to their views of different methods. The following exploratory research questions were investigated:

- Which differences exist between chemical risk assessors and the public's perspectives on (next generation) chemical risk assessment?

- What are chemical risk assessors' perspectives of the future of risk assessment and are they related to their views of different methods (in vivo, in vitro, in silico)?

The article focuses on human health risk assessors' and the public's trust in the results of in vivo, in vitro, and in silico studies for identifying a hazard or for describing the toxicity of a substance, their views of positive versus negative results of in vivo and in vitro studies, and transferability of findings across similar substances (i.e., read-across/grouping).

3 | METHODOLOGY

3.1 | Design and procedure

This study is based on two anonymous online surveys, one with the German-speaking public of Switzerland in German and the other with European risk assessors in English. Participants from the public were recruited through a market research company (Bilendi & respondi). A quota design based on sex and five age groups ensured a more heterogeneous sample. The human health risk assessors were recruited as part of a larger project within the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC, <https://www.eu-parc.eu/>) funded under Horizon Europe. Both surveys featured identical questions. The section on the risk assessors' perspectives on in vivo, in vitro, and in silico testing was an optional part of a larger questionnaire. Both surveys comprised additional sections, which will be reported elsewhere (public survey: perceptions of animal testing, replication of two unrelated experiments; risk assessor survey: technical sections on the status quo of acceptance and use of NAMs). Participation was anonymous, and all participants provided informed consent at the start of the survey. Ethical approval was sought for both surveys prior to data collection (public survey: EK 2023-N-53; chemical risk assessor survey: EK 2023-N-12).

3.2 | Questionnaire

It was assumed that participants from the public would be familiar with the term "animal testing" for in vivo testing. However, in vitro and in silico tests were introduced as "cell testing" and "computer models" with the following introductory texts:

- in vitro: cell testing—safety assessment using cells in test tubes or Petri dishes (e.g., bacteria, animal, or human cells)
- in silico: computer models—estimation of safety by computer models or simulations based on data collected in animal or cell experiments in the past.

The public's and the risk assessors' perspectives on in vivo, in vitro, and in silico testing were assessed with the same

set of questions, which were adapted from previous studies (Kraus et al., 1992; Slovic et al., 1995) (cf. Table 1). Specifically, the items covered the degree of agreement that in vivo, in vitro, and in silico tests can identify harmful effects of a chemical and accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans. Moreover, the items covered the implications of a positive versus a negative result of an in vivo versus in vitro study. One item covered the agreement with a precondition of read-across or grouping: similarity of substances and deduction of harmfulness. The items were introduced with the following question: "Please indicate to what extent you agree with each of the following statements" and were slightly simplified for the version for the public (i.e., animal testing instead of in vivo testing, cell testing instead of in vitro testing, computer models instead of in silico). The Likert scale responses were labeled and varied from 1 "do not agree at all" to 4 "fully agree." Additionally, there was a fifth option to indicate "do not know/no opinion."

The risk assessors were additionally asked about their perspectives of the future of risk assessment and the roles different methods play in it (e.g., NGRA and AI). Due to their complexity, these questions were not posed to the public participants. Figure 1 presents the five items.

3.3 | Data analysis

To compare the frequency of agreement and disagreement among different risk assessors and the public on the individual items, descriptive analyses of the response distributions and Pearson's Chi-square tests were done. Additionally, the responses of the risk assessors regarding the future of risk assessment were descriptively analyzed and linked to their perspectives on in vivo, in vitro, and in silico testing through bivariate correlations (Spearman, "do not know/no opinion" responses were coded as missing values for this). All analyses were conducted in IBM SPSS Statistics 28.0 (IBM Corp, 2021).

4 | RESULTS

4.1 | Sample description

A total sample of $N = 965$ participants from the public were recruited ($n = 463$ male, $n = 499$ female, $n = 3$ diverse; $M_{\text{age}} = 45$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 15$, age range: 18–70). A total sample of $N = 222$ human health risk assessors was recruited within the larger study within PARC. For this article, only the risk assessors who agreed to fill out the optional part on the perspectives of risk assessment were retained. This resulted in a final sample of $N = 131$ human health risk assessors ($n = 58$ male, $n = 68$ female, $n = 2$ diverse, $n = 5$ did not want to indicate their gender; $M_{\text{age}} = 48$, $SD_{\text{age}} = 12$, age range: 28–77). Most risk assessors worked in Western Europe ($n = 82$, 62%), followed by Northern Europe ($n = 34$,

TABLE 1 Response distributions of perspectives on risk assessment (survey with the public: $N = 965$, survey with risk assessors: $N = 131$).

		1. Strongly disagree	2. Disagree	3. Agree	4. Strongly agree	5. Do not know/no opinion
Trust in hazard identification						
In vivo studies of a chemical's effect on whole animals can identify harmful effects of a chemical in humans ^a	RA	2 (2%)	4 (3%)	71 (54%)	54 (41%)	0 (0%)
	P	72 (7%)	95 (10%)	486 (50%)	85 (9%)	227 (24%)
In vitro studies of a chemical's effect on a cell or cell structure can identify harmful effects of a chemical in humans ^a	RA	2 (1%)	10 (8%)	89 (68%)	29 (22%)	1 (1%)
	P	30 (3%)	64 (6%)	508 (53%)	106 (11%)	257 (27%)
In silico studies that simulate a chemical's effect can identify harmful effects of a chemical in humans ^a	RA	1 (1%)	13 (10%)	95 (73%)	19 (14%)	3 (2%)
	P	60 (6%)	207 (21%)	289 (30%)	64 (7%)	345 (36%)
Trust in describing the toxicity						
In vivo studies allow to accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans ^a	RA	1 (1%)	36 (27%)	63 (48%)	26 (20%)	5 (4%)
	P	155 (16%)	212 (22%)	284 (29%)	55 (6%)	259 (27%)
In vitro studies allow to accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans ^a	RA	4 (3%)	48 (36%)	67 (51%)	7 (5%)	6 (5%)
	P	46 (5%)	153 (16%)	365 (38%)	91 (9%)	310 (32%)
In silico studies allow to accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans ^a	RA	7 (5%)	62 (48%)	50 (38%)	4 (3%)	8 (6%)
	P	111 (11%)	250 (26%)	205 (21%)	45 (5%)	354 (37%)
Views of positive vs. negative results						
If an in vivo study produces evidence that a chemical causes harm, we can be reasonably sure that the chemical will cause harm in humans ^a	RA	5 (4%)	46 (35%)	63 (48%)	15 (12%)	2 (1%)
	P	80 (8%)	109 (11%)	432 (45%)	130 (14%)	214 (22%)
If an in vivo study produces evidence that a chemical does not cause harm, we can be reasonably sure that the chemical will not cause harm in humans ^a	RA	7 (5%)	65 (49%)	47 (36%)	6 (5%)	6 (5%)
	P	85 (9%)	194 (20%)	297 (31%)	52 (5%)	337 (35%)
If an in vitro study produces evidence that a chemical causes harm, we can be reasonably sure that the chemical will cause harm in humans ^a	RA	9 (7%)	67 (51%)	45 (34%)	5 (4%)	5 (4%)
	P	32 (3%)	67 (7%)	464 (48%)	141 (15%)	261 (27%)
If an in vitro study produces evidence that a chemical does not cause harm, we can be reasonably sure that the chemical will not cause harm in humans ^a	RA	16 (12%)	83 (63%)	24 (18%)	2 (2%)	6 (5%)
	P	40 (4%)	139 (14%)	358 (37%)	72 (8%)	356 (37%)
Transferability across substances						
If two substances are very similar, data on one substance can be used to deduce whether the other substance is harmful ^a	RA	4 (3%)	19 (14%)	89 (68%)	16 (12%)	3 (3%)
	P	64 (7%)	175 (18%)	293 (30%)	54 (6%)	379 (39%)

Note: RA: survey with the risk assessors, P: survey with the public.

^aDifferent response distribution for risk assessors and the public according to the Pearson Chi-square test ($p < 0.001$). White color-coding indicates low response rates per cell (<25%). Light gray color-coding indicates medium response rates per cell (25%–50%), and Medium gray color-coding indicates higher response rates per cell (>50%).

25%), Southern Europe ($n = 16$, 12%), and Eastern Europe ($n = 1$, 1%). The risk assessors were asked to indicate in which discipline(s) they had received significant formal training from a multiple-choice list with multiple entries possible. The most frequently chosen disciplines were toxicology ($n = 119$, 90%), risk assessment ($n = 83$, 62%), biology ($n = 78$, 59%), biochemistry ($n = 69$, 52%), and chemistry ($n = 65$, 49%). Other disciplines, such as engineering, ecology/environmental sciences, computer science/mathematics, public and occupational health, medicine, pharmaceutical sciences, veterinary sciences, and epidemiology, were chosen less frequently (<25%).

4.2 | The risk assessors versus the public's perspectives on risk assessment

Table 1 presents the response distributions from the public and the risk assessors. For ease of interpretation, the table is color-coded with darker grays indicating higher response rates per cell (>50%), medium response rates per cell (25%–50%), or low response rates per cell (<25%). All Pearson's Chi-square tests were statistically significant, $\chi^2(4) > 50.6$, $p < 0.001$. Unsurprisingly, the largest differences in responses by risk assessors and the public originated in the “do not know/no opinion category”: More participants from the

FIGURE 1 Risk assessors' perspectives on the future of risk assessment (N = 131).

public indicated that they did not know or had no opinion (on average 31% of the sample) compared to the risk assessors (on average 5% of the sample). For ease of interpretation, in the description of the results below, the percentages of agreement and strong agreement were added up. Table 1 shows the detailed responses, differentiated by agreement and strong agreement.

The risk assessors were mostly in agreement or strong agreement that *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and, to a lesser degree, *in silico* testing can identify harmful effects in humans, as 95%, 90%, and 87% (strongly) agreed. The public was more skeptical of *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and particularly regarding *in silico* testing, with 59%, 64%, and 37% agreeing or strongly agreeing that these methods can identify harmful effects in humans.¹ Both risk assessors and the public were less convinced that *in vivo* (68% and 35% agreement or strong agreement), *in vitro* (56% and 47% agreement or strong agreement), and, particularly, *in silico* testing (41% and 26% agreement or strong agreement) would accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans.

The risk assessors varied in their trust in the informative value of a positive (i.e., results suggest that the chemical is harmful) and a negative (i.e., results suggest that the chemical is not harmful) *in vivo/in vitro* test outcome, with more trust in positive results (60%/38% agreement or strong agreement) than in negative results (41%/20% agreement or strong agreement). For positive/negative outcomes, *in vivo* (60%/41% agreement or strong agreement) elicited lower uncertainty among risk assessors than *in vitro* tests (38%/20% agreement

or strong agreement). The public expressed similar differences in the trust in the informative value of positive versus negative *in vivo/in vitro* test outcomes, with more trust in positive results (59%/63% agreement or strong agreement) than in negative results (36%/45% agreement or strong agreement). However, other than the risk assessors, *in vitro* testing (63%/45% agreement or strong agreement) elicited similarly high or higher trust than *in vivo* testing (59%/36% agreement or strong agreement) for positive/negative results.

Lastly, more risk assessors expressed agreement or strong agreement (80% agreement or strong agreement) regarding the transferability of insights across substances than participants from the public (36% agreement or strong agreement).

4.3 | The risk assessors' perspectives on the future of risk assessment

Figure 1 shows how the risk assessors viewed the future of risk assessment regarding different concepts and methods. Agreement was high for three of the statements (>80% agreement or strong agreement): Most risk assessors agreed that risk assessment will remain the primary tool to ensure human and environmental safety and that it must evolve to meet future societal, ethical, and policy needs and that a change in legislative frameworks is needed for a successful implementation of NAMs. More risk assessors disagreed that did not know or had no opinion whether digitalization will be instrumental in NGRA (19% disagreement or strong disagreement and 18% do not know/no opinion) and regarding the role of the testing of whole animals in NGRA (57% disagreement or strong disagreement and 15% uncertain).

Table 2 shows the Spearman correlation coefficients for each perspective on the future of risk assessment and the

¹ The "do not know" responses do not fully account for the differences between risk assessors and the public, as all ($\chi^2(3) > 16.1, p < 0.001$) but one Chi-square test ($\chi^2(3) = 6.2, p = 0.104$; "In vitro studies of a chemical's effect on a cell or cell structure can identify harmful effects of a chemical in humans") remained significant when the "do not know" responses were treated as missing values.

TABLE 2 Spearman correlation coefficients between perspectives on the future of risk assessment and trust in different methods (survey with risk assessors: $N = 131$).

	In vivo studies of a chemical's effect on whole animals can identify harmful effects of a chemical in humans	In vitro studies of a chemical's effect on a cell or cell structure can identify harmful effects of a chemical in humans	In silico studies that simulate a chemical's effect can identify harmful effects of a chemical in humans	In vivo studies allow to accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans	In vitro studies allow to accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans	In silico studies allow to accurately describe the toxicity of a chemical in humans
Risk assessment will remain the primary tool for ensuring human and environmental safety in the future	0.27**	0.04	-0.14	0.21*	0.09	0.01
Risk assessment must evolve to meet future societal, ethical, and/or policy needs	0.01	0.23**	0.17	-0.13	0.12	0.10
A successful implementation of NAMs in regulatory risk assessment is only possible if the legislative framework changes	0.08	0.13	0.08	0.09	0.25**	0.18*
Digitalization (e.g., artificial intelligence) will be instrumental in paving the way forward to next-generation risk assessment	-0.01	0.22*	0.27**	-0.07	0.25**	0.35***
The concept of next-generation risk assessment is not compatible with animal testing	0.00	0.33***	0.24*	0.04	0.08	0.10

Abbreviation: NAM, new approach methodology.

* $p < 0.05$,

** $p < 0.01$,

*** $p < 0.001$.

risk assessors' trust in *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and *in silico* testing. Some interesting patterns emerged from these coefficients. Participants that indicated higher trust in *in vivo* studies expressed more agreement that risk assessment is the primary tool for ensuring human and environmental safety in the future, whereas a higher trust in *in vitro* studies coincided with a higher agreement about the need for risk assessment to evolve. A higher trust in *in vitro* and *in silico* studies for describing toxicity (but not for hazard identification) coincided with a higher agreement that a legislative change is needed for the successful implementation of NAMs. A higher trust in *in vitro* and *in silico* studies was related to a higher agreement regarding the role of digitalization in NGRA (i.e., AI), and higher trust in *in vitro* and *in silico* stud-

ies regarding hazard identification coincided with a higher agreement regarding the incompatibility of animal testing in NGRA.

5 | DISCUSSION

5.1 | Summary and interpretation of results regarding risk assessors

The results of this study show heterogeneity regarding the perspectives of risk assessors of *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and *in silico* testing. Most risk assessors (around 90%) agreed that these tests were able to identify harmful effects in humans

and were more divided regarding the tests' ability to describe toxicity (with a third to two thirds agreement). The divide among risk assessors regarding the alternatives to *in vivo* testing mirrors the documented uncertainty regarding alternatives to *in vivo* testing among the risk assessment community (e.g., Ball et al., 2022; Mondou et al., 2020; Schmeisser et al., 2023). The risk assessors' background and formal training might explain some of these findings. For example, traditionally, toxicologists might put more thought into thresholds for harm, whereas geneticists or ecologists might consider the possibility of harm independent of the dose, which is the basis for the different regulations of carcinogens and other substances in the USA (Hattis et al., 2002). Equally, different disciplines might differ in their familiarity with *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and *in silico* approaches. Although some risk assessors might feel comfortable interpreting *in vivo* or *in vitro* test results, they might feel uncertain about using computer-based or AI-supported models due to their lack of experience and training in this field. Due to the complex mix of each risk assessors' background, disciplines, and formal training, these relationships should best be explored in a qualitative approach (e.g., focus groups with risk assessors with different backgrounds).

5.2 | Summary and interpretation of results regarding the public

The results further suggest that the public did not necessarily use the perceived complexity of the underlying model as a heuristic strategy to judge the validity of the test. Rather, the public expressed trust in *in vitro* testing, in some cases even more than in *in vivo* testing, for hazard identification and description of toxicity. Multiple factors might explain the higher trust of the public in *in vitro* compared to *in vivo* testing. First and foremost, the public might have perceived a more direct link between *in vitro* and potential harm to human health compared to *in vivo* testing, as it was highlighted that human cells are used. Second, the public might be critical of *in vivo* testing, view it as a necessary evil, and, therefore, welcome approaches that do not involve live animals (e.g., Masterton et al., 2014; Petetta & Ciccocioppo, 2020; Swami et al., 2008). These views might color their responses through heuristic thinking (i.e., the affect heuristic), eliciting negative affect for *in vivo* and positive affect for *in vitro* testing (Slovic et al., 2004, 2007). It is also possible that other heuristic thinking is at work here (e.g., availability heuristic and halo effect) but this would need to be evaluated in more detail in future studies. Third, the approaches differ in their use of specialized language (e.g., animal testing is likely more familiar terminology than cell testing in test tubes or Petri dishes or computer simulations), which might have further served as cues to judge complexity by the public.

5.3 | Summary and interpretation of results regarding both groups

Both participant groups perceived positive outcomes as more certain than negative outcomes, independent of the type of test, which mirrors prior studies on positive versus negative outcomes (Siegrist & Cvetkovich, 2001; White et al., 2003) and the negativity bias, which states that negative events or information more strongly impact human cognition, judgments and decision-making than positive ones (Hilbig, 2009; Ito et al., 1998; Poortinga & Pidgeon, 2004; Rozin & Royzman, 2001). Particularly, the negativity bias might be a useful decision strategy to people who are uncertain or do not hold strong preexisting attitudes regarding a particular topic (Poortinga & Pidgeon, 2004; White et al., 2003). The public was particularly unsure whether insights can be transferred from one substance to another, highlighting a potential challenge for the future. This might in parts be explained by the more extensive knowledge that risk assessors have of the structure of chemicals and by the risk assessors' awareness of data gaps and the need to analyze a large amount of possibly hazardous chemicals or chemical mixtures.

Both these topics (i.e., implications of positive vs. negative outcomes, structural similarity, and predictivity) are linked to uncertainty, which can be difficult to quantify and communicate to experts, such as risk managers, policy makers, and other actors, and more importantly, to the lay public (Jansen et al., 2019; Spiegelhalter, 2017). It is important to note that communicating uncertainty can lead to cognitive overload, hamper decision-making, and can negatively impact trust in science and experts among the public (Fischhoff & Davis, 2014; Van Der Bles et al., 2019). Future risk communication research could utilize current frameworks and approaches to transparency in science (Blastland et al., 2020; Elliott, 2022; Van Der Bles et al., 2019) to develop creative and tailored ways to communicate epistemic uncertainty to different groups.

5.4 | The future of chemical risk assessment

As the scientific and regulatory community debates what NGRA should look like (Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023; Pallocca et al., 2022) and which preconditions warrant the replacement of *in vivo* testing with alternatives (e.g., Dent et al., 2021; Schmeisser et al., 2023), the views of individual risk assessors need to be taken into account (i.e., their preferences, views, needs, and attitudes). Our study suggests that for risk assessors, *in vivo* testing—albeit not perfect—is generally still considered the gold standard, when compared to *in vitro* or *in silico* approaches. This is a substantial barrier to the regulatory acceptance and use of the alternatives, which will require time, stakeholder engagement, change managements, and showcasing successful uses of alternatives in chemical risk assessment to overcome.

Studies suggest that the major barriers to the acceptance and use of NAMs in risk assessment are of a structural nature (e.g., missing standardization of approaches and lack of transferability) (Schmeisser et al., 2023; Zaunbrecher et al., 2017). However, changes to the regulatory structures occur due to a growing need from stakeholders and must continuously be carried by the involved stakeholders. Schmeisser et al. (2023) have summarized what these needs might be and specifically highlight the shortcomings of *in vivo* testing in chemical risk assessment in light of the number of chemicals and mixtures that need testing. However, our findings show that aside from structural barriers, alternatives to *in vivo* testing might also encounter individual-level opposition due to the increased perceived and real uncertainty. A fundamental question for the future is how to tackle this uncertainty of using alternatives for hazard or risk assessment among risk assessors. Aside from demonstrating equal levels of safety compared to established methods and quantifying the associated uncertainty, the way alternatives and accompanying information (e.g., about uncertainty and about relevance) are presented to risk assessors, and risk managers might also substantially impact their credibility and thus, the success of alternatives for regulatory purposes. More interdisciplinary collaboration, involving the social sciences, is needed to inform efforts to use innovative approaches and models (Patterson & Whelan, 2017).

5.5 | Limitations and implications for future research

The study has some limitations. First, the public data was collected in the German-speaking part of Switzerland in German, whereas the risk assessor data was collected in English from various European countries, including Switzerland. It is unlikely that the responses of the public would differ substantially across countries, as it is to be expected that knowledge of toxicological principles is low across Europe (Bearth et al., 2019). However, the different languages and the different contexts of the studies might have introduced some biases in the responses of the participants. Future studies could replicate the findings in other European countries and include further explanatory variables to investigate the individual differences in responses (e.g., trust in risk assessment). In a related matter, the quota design for the sample from the public ensured heterogeneity in gender and age and similar distributions as in the population of the German-speaking part of Switzerland. However, we are hesitant to call this a representative sample, as other national language areas (i.e., French, Italian, and Rhaeto-Romanic) were missing and participants had to be willing to participate in an online survey.

Second, it is important to note that the questions included in both surveys were simplified. This was done in a similar fashion as the original articles (Kraus et al., 1992; Slovic et al., 1995) and was necessary due to the complexity of the subject at hand and the relatively low knowledge among the public about chemical risk assessment (Bearth et al.,

2019, 2020; Saleh et al., 2019). As the presented items were unspecific regarding the type of test, application context, and endpoint, risk assessors might have struggled with responding to these simple examples or the heterogeneity in responses might originate from thinking of different specific cases. Considering the current regulatory landscape in Europe, the assessment and management of a substance is not based on a single *in vivo*, *in vitro*, or *in silico* test but on the weighing or synthesis of multiple lines of evidence from different evidence streams (including human epidemiological and mechanistic studies in addition to the previously cited). Moreover, the terms used (i.e., *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and *in silico*) comprise a multitude of very different tests, as *in silico* might imply representations of physiology or might comprise the interpretation of patterns found in large data. This highlights the hypothetical nature of the questions for the risk assessors, which would make it harder for them to respond to them. However, this limitation was unavoidable to compare public and risk assessors' perspectives, and the relatively low frequency of "do not know/no opinion" responses suggests that risk assessors were able to form an opinion about the individual items. Despite the insights generated in the pretest, it remains unclear whether all participants from the public understood "toxicity of a chemical" and differentiated between hazard identification and describing toxicity. Prior research suggests that the public is unlikely to consider dose-response when judging the potential harm, a chemical might do (Bearth et al., 2016; Saleh et al., 2019; Slovic et al., 1995), which might have further complicated the judgment of this item. Future studies could consider qualitative approaches to investigate these issues in more depth.

Third, this study featured a Likert scale with four response options (strongly disagree, disagree, agree, and strongly agree) and one option to indicate "do not know/no opinion." This was done in line with prior research (Kraus et al., 1992; Slovic et al., 1995) for comparison purposes. While not surprising, it is worth noting that the participants from the public more frequently picked the latter option. It is possible that similar differences in response patterns could also apply to the other four response options (e.g., different assumptions or the interpretation of the distance between strong agreement and agreement for risk assessors compared to the public). This is a methodological limitation that might account for some of the differences observed in risk assessors and public response patterns.

6 | Conclusion

This study aimed at contributing to the discussion on the use of alternative testing methods (i.e., *in vitro* and *in silico*) for NGRA by highlighting that individual risk assessors are more skeptical regarding alternatives than regarding whole animal (*in vivo*) testing. Future studies should not only think about structural ways to change chemical risk assessment but also come up with ways to improve risk assessors' trust in the viability and validity of alternative testing methods and

reduce the perceived uncertainty linked to the use of these alternatives. Lastly, the study offers insights into potential challenges in chemical risk communication with the public. Although the results suggest that the increased use of in vitro testing might not suggest higher uncertainty or risk to the public compared to in vivo testing, the use of in silico testing or read-across methods might.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The survey with the public was funded internally. Part of this work (i.e., the survey with the risk assessors) was carried out in the framework of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) and has received funding from the Federal Office of Public Health and the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the Federal Office of Public Health, the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Open access funding provided by Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zurich.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

FUNDING INFORMATION

European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC); Federal Office of Public Health and the European Union's Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No.: 101057014

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that supports the findings of this study will be made publicly available upon publication.

ORCID

Angela Bearth <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1270-6468>

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How to cite this article: Bearth, A., Roth, N., Wilks, M. F., & Siegrist, M. (2024). Intuitive toxicology in the 21st century—Bridging the perspectives of the public and risk assessors in Europe. *Risk Analysis*, 44, 2348–2359. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.14296>